

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SULEMANA****FIRST NAME: AMINU****PROGRAM CODE : DME****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord- office 365 on MacOS Ventura 13.2.1)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In academic writing, plagiarism constitutes.

- When a writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of the information.¹**
- When a writer paraphrases a source of information with appropriate citation.
- When a writer directly quotes a source of information with appropriate citation.
- When a writer uses information and appropriately references the source of information.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition. (Bangui: Euclid University), 2021, 34.

2. Paraphrasing in academic writing means.
- Express the ideas and information of an author using the same style and appropriately cite the source.
 - Express the ideas and information of an author using a language that resembles the author's words and appropriately cite the source.
 - Express the ideas and information of an author on a topic in your own words and appropriately cite the source.²**
 - Express the ideas and information different from the author's original ideas and appropriately cite the source.
3. A research argument in academic writing refers to.
- Intimidating one's opponent into assent or silence.
 - Conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues.³**
 - Manipulating one's opponent into assent without evidence.
 - Subduing one's opponent into assent or silence.
4. To avoid the judgment in research that your paper is just a data dump.
- You need a problem, one that is focused on finding just the data that will help you solve it.⁴**
 - You need general research questions to help you gather data to solve the problem.

² Ibid., 36.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (University of Chicago Press, 2018), 56.

⁴ Ibid., 29.

- You need to find answers that are similar to existing research work.
 - You need a research topic to guide you to gather data.
5. The following depicts the importance of secondary sources of data except.
- Help researchers to keep up with current research.
 - Help researchers to find other points of view.
 - Help researchers to find models for their own research.
 - Help researchers to obtain raw data or evidence.**⁵
6. In academic writing, the researcher gives credit to the research and reassures readers about the accuracy of the facts by.
- Citing and referencing all the sources of information.**⁶
 - Citing and referencing some of the sources of information.
 - Citing and referencing their own work only.
 - None of the above.
7. The following refers to situations where the researcher needs to cite the source of the information used, except.
- When the researcher quotes exact words from a source.
 - When the researcher paraphrases ideas that are associated with a specific source.

⁵ Ibid., 36.

⁶ Ibid., 139.

When the researcher uses his own ideals.⁷

When the researcher uses any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source he consulted.

8. In the author-date style of citation.

The author's name, date, and relevant pages are placed in parentheses next to the reference.⁸

A superscript is placed after the author's name, date, and relevant pages next to the reference.

A subscript is placed after the author's name, date, and relevant pages next to the reference.

The author's name, date, and relevant pages are put in quotation marks next to the reference.

9. According to the dissertation research guide, the literature review chapter of the dissertation should aim at.

Helping the reader understand the methods used in the dissertation.

Helping the reader understand the limitations of the dissertation.

Help the reader understand the variables that will be examined in the dissertation.⁹

⁷ Ibid., 82.

⁸ Ibid., 142.

⁹ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition. (Florida State University, Florida, 2017), 31.

Helping the reader understand the conclusions of the dissertation.

10. According to the dissertation research guide, the hypothesis is stated.

Either null or directional.¹⁰

Both null and directional.

With necessary references.

With research questions.

¹⁰ Ibid., 35.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Florida State University, Florida, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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